

MUSEUMS AND DIGITAL ERA

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the information about museum technologies and their virtual opportunities is given. Museums have started use contemporary digital communication technologies to meet customers' expectations. Social media accounts, smartphone applications and virtual tours have become popular. Museum curators and directors are developing different forms of exhibition. Chosen exhibition methods provide an opportunity to interact with artworks efficiently using multiple senses which is incredibly important to create satisfying museum experience. Museum collections can be displayed with different audio devices, mechanical-electronic models, interactive sources of information and lighting devices.

Why museum technologies are needed? In order to fulfill social functions, museums use a collection of resources, techniques, strategies and professional actions and technologies. Because exhibitions, savings, improvement of museum management, development of potential cultural and educational activities and marketing strategies rely on technological advancement.

Keywords: multiple senses, sensors, sensitive panels, projection mapping, multiple projection.

Karayilanog'lu(2020) stated that It is wide knowledge that culture is abstract and complex, it is considered as universal meaning and condition of human existence, cultural and artistic works are universal heritage objects of humanity. Science and technology can likewise be results of human accumulation achieved by human brains through the world.

All artistic activities, entertainment circulations and media tools can be intertwined in our era. Art objects can be produced, represented and consumed by digital possibilities and digital exhibitions include all together simultaneously.

Virtual and augmented reality can implement the architectures and artifacts of museum spaces. We can not ignore the sociological effects of technology.

Nowadays, visitors have high expectations regarding technical possibilities of museums. We can achieve the increasing trend in the use of technological

advancements in cultural entertainment-oriented activities through including users.

Museum should enhance user experience-oriented applications, visitors realize and perceive their surrounding through their senses and comprehension. This relevant action takes place within ongoing timeframe and which can change with several factors such as the actualization of senses, the length of experience and the emotional condition of visitor. Luis.D., Rivero.M.(2018).

Digital interactive technologies can influence the multi-layered experiences of visitors addressing the senses of them. Technical possibilities have started to be used in museum spaces in 1920s in European countries.

High-tech communication tools such as augmented reality, virtual reality have been considerably used in art museums in the latest years. Despite of the maintainance of static exhibition systems, new mixed exhibition system is being activated and implemented as an unusual and interactive spatial experience. New technologies can be divided into two types: active and passive interactive digital technologies.

Passive interactive technologies:

Projection mapping, sound systems, digital displays, sensors

Active interactive technologies:

Touch screens, quick response code implementations, virtual reality, augmented reality, mixed reality, artificial intelligence applications.

Digital screens are used to demonstrate different videos and photographic images in modern museums. Digital displays are combined with sound systems which do not require active participation of visitors and interact with individual's perception and opinion.

Audio signals are recorded, stored and processed by using digital audio technologies. Sound systems can implement the meaning of artworks to create special atmosphere of space.

Projection mapping

Projection devices are used in schools, offices and museums. It can temporarily change the atmosphere of space by making videos and light reflections. The concept of projection mapping emerged recently, for instance, while performing arts, stage design can be changed often.

Today it is possible to revive ancient cultural heritage due to projection mapping. As a result of natural disasters, political wars, the inherited cultural objects were destroyed. Disappeared artworks have started living virtually, such as Buha statue in Afghanistan which was demolished by Taliban in 2001. After

that, the 3 D image of that sculpture was created in May 2019. It is clear that these images are only reproduced artworks which are created by integrating all the data of artwork and this can offer attainability of transferring these cultural objects to the future offspring in detail. More broadly, it can be considered as a new technique of archiving. Multiple projectors are used to represent 3D images on all surfaces of museum spaces. Comprehensive museum experiences should be combined with visuals, lights and sounds. The intended consequences of combination of entertainment -oriented experiences are the alteration of total museum perception. Various interactive shows are represented using projection mapping technologies including sensors, multiple projectors and digital cameras.

Sensors

The process of activating data using sensors such as heat, sound, motion, light and pressure is generated by the sensors which does not require active participatory of visitors including indirect interaction with museum environment. The museum sensitive sensors can offer the possibility of determination of the number of visitors and projection of user movements. Sensors have an opportunity of determination of visitor movement in a desired area and a reflection of an image on digital screens at the same time. These images move and interact with the users simultaneously. It is also indirect connection between museum and a visitor. Because they are included in the projection, irrespective how much they are aware or not.

Another milestone of museum sensors is that they can be used as the alarm systems which can install immaterial border between art objects and users. Thus, an automatic warning can be given for being crossed an inappropriate distance with an artwork.

Active Interactive Digital Technologies

These technologies include touch screens, quick response codes, virtual reality, augmented reality, mixed reality and artificial implementation.

Touch screens

The sensitive panels can be activated with the fingertips of visitor or special pens. It is broad knowledge that touch screens are used in our daily lives and those are of utmost importance of creating a satisfying museum experience. Touch screen technology is used in museums for kiosks, tablets and information panels.

Any errors in information board can be corrected instantly. The exhibition catalogues and layouts can be distributed through museum area with touch

screens in a shorter time. Multiple users can interact directly with touch screens to get information about artworks which can offer thematic grouping system and visitors can download the images of artworks via Bluetooth which are virtually chosen by visitors.

Quick response codes

QR codes are widely used in museums to expand the accessibility of visitors to the interactivity technologies. QR codes can be added to the tags of artworks and visitors can use bigger sources of information about artworks in detail which can significantly reduce the need for informative writing while creating the interior design of museums and highlights the visuality in a museum.

Visitor can transmit any information which is preferable. Museum smartphones and applications can contribute to exceed the satisfaction of museum visitors. The aim for using these technologies is to find the QR codes of artworks within seconds with their built-in cameras which detect short videos about the curation process of the artworks. In addition to this, the process of finding a QR code can be organized as a funny educational game to provide fulfilling museum experience.

In digital era, virtual museums have emerged as a result of technological development. "Virtual" was originally comes from the word "virtus", which means "imagination". In a special place virtual museum is designed with museum artifacts. If we visit virtual museum via web connection, we can watch exhibits from various points. It is an invented museum model which was created with computer technologies, exhibits only exist in a virtual environment. Schweibenz.W (2004). Also, this kind of museum can reflect several components of a real museum such as "collection catalog. Virtual exhibitions allow visitors to interact with each other, and they can obtain virtual copies of objects which can offer virtual travel around the museum. This method was invented and performed at the Van Gogh Museum where screens show different virtual objects in a regular basis. The moving animated artworks reflect a unique composition of exhibits according to the book of Terms of Tangible and Intangible Heritage Of Uzbekistan.

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